

Energy security: The World's Last Parachute

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Abstract

Energy security is the association between national security and the availability of natural resources for energy consumption. Access to (relatively) cheap energy has become essential to the functioning of modern economies. However, the uneven distribution of energy supplies among countries has led to significant vulnerabilities. International energy relations have contributed to the globalization of the world leading to energy security and energy vulnerability at the same time. Renewable resources and significant opportunities for energy efficiency and transitions exist over wide geographical areas, in contrast to other energy sources, which are concentrated in a limited number of countries. Rapid deployment of renewable energy and energy efficiency, and technological diversification of energy sources, would result in significant energy security and economic benefits.

New threats to energy security have emerged in the form of the increased world competition for energy resources due to the increased pace of industrialization in countries such as India and China, as well as due to the increasing consequences of climate change. Although still a minority concern, the possibility of price rises resulting from the peaking of world oil production is also starting to attract the attention of at least the French government. Increased competition over energy resources may also lead to the formation of security compacts to enable an equitable distribution of oil and gas between major powers. However, this may happen at the expense of less developed economies.

Recent Publications

1. Ang, Beng Wah, Wei Lim Choong, and Tsan Sheng Ng. "Energy security: Definitions, dimensions and indexes." *Renewable and sustainable energy reviews* 42 (2015): 1077-1093.
2. Cherp, Aleh, and Jessica Jewell. "The concept of energy security: Beyond the four As." *Energy policy* 75 (2014): 415-421.
3. Song, Yan, Ming Zhang, and Ruifeng Sun. "Using a new aggregated indicator to evaluate China's energy security." *Energy Policy* 132 (2019): 167-174.
4. Augutis, Juozas, et al. "Analysis of energy security level in the Baltic States based on indicator approach." *Energy* 199 (2020): 117427.

Biography

Pourya Zarshenas was born in 1994, Tehran-Iran. He started B.Sc in 2013 at Shahid Beheshti University. He finished B.Sc in 2018. Immediately he Started M.Sc in 2018 at Shahid Beheshti University in Inorganic chemistry. He finished his Master in 2020. His thesis title is: "Design & identification of polymer nanocomposite as an eye sensor for toxic metal ions such as mercury, lead, etc. in aqueous media". He wants continue his academic education in Inorganic chemistry, crystal engineering & Polymer Chemistry.

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